

Schools at Risk: Mapping Learning Poverty in Italian Schools

**Lidia Rossi¹, Mara Soncin¹, Melisa Diaz Lema¹,
Tommaso Agasisti¹**

1. Politecnico di Milano, School of Management

Summary

1. The study investigates how administrative and assessment data in Italy can be used to predict the share of students at risk of learning poverty at the school level, rather than at the individual level, in order to better prioritise dropout-prevention policies and avoid stigmatising individual students.
2. Socioeconomic status and prior achievement are the strongest predictors of learning poverty, but several organisational factors also matter.
3. Protective factors include kindergarten attendance, teacher stability, municipal funding, experienced principals, and digital communication with families, while teacher absenteeism, late enrolment, language barriers, and high transfer rates are associated with higher risk.
4. The results suggest that policy-makers should use predictive analytics to target support to high-risk schools, strengthen teacher stability and early childhood participation, encourage local co-investment and parental engagement, and promote peer learning from resilient schools, while adopting territorially differentiated policies to address persistent regional disparities in learning outcomes.

1. Introduction

Learning poverty – the failure of children to attain minimum literacy and numeracy thresholds by the end of lower secondary school – represents one of the most pressing challenges for the Italian educational system. Students who fall below these thresholds are substantially more likely to drop out before completing compulsory education, with well-documented life-long consequences for earnings, health, and civic participation. Early identification of the schools that concentrate the highest shares of at-risk students is a

prerequisite for effective, targeted public intervention. Yet the existing literature has overwhelmingly focused on predicting risk at the individual student level, without aggregating this information at the school level. Focusing on schools rather than students offers at least two advantages: it supports priority-setting under constrained budgets, and it avoids the stigmatisation that can follow from labelling individual pupils as 'at risk'.

Against this backdrop, the paper asks two research questions:

- How accurately can Italian administrative data predict the share of students at risk of learning poverty within a school, so as to prioritise dropout-prevention interventions?
- Which school-related factors are associated with a smaller or larger share of at-risk students – especially in socioeconomically deprived contexts?

Why this matters for policy? Italy's INVALSI standardised assessments provide a nationally comparable measure of minimum competence in mathematics and reading at the end of Grade 8 (age ~13–14). By combining this information with administrative data from the Ministry of Education, it becomes possible, for the first time, to profile every public lower-secondary school in the country on its learning-poverty exposure – and to identify which school-level factors can be leveraged even when the socioeconomic context is unfavourable.

2. Data and Methods

The study draws on a novel linked dataset covering all 4,895 public lower-secondary schools (Grade 8, A.Y. 2018–2019) in mainland Italy and the main islands, excluding the autonomous provinces of Trento and Bolzano. Two complementary sources are merged for the first time:

- INVALSI test results – providing school-level shares of students scoring at or below Level 2 (the 'at risk' threshold) in standardised mathematics and reading assessments.
- Ministry of Education administrative data – covering student composition and demographics; school transfers;

funding sources and expenditure purposes; teaching staff characteristics (tenure, age, experience, absenteeism); school principal characteristics; and parental involvement instruments.

Four outcome variables are modelled: the share of at-risk students in reading, in mathematics, in at least one subject, and in both subjects simultaneously. On average, 37% of students are at risk in reading and 42% in mathematics, rising to 50% at risk in at least one subject and 28% in both.

The analytical strategy uses multilevel linear regression models in which schools are nested within provinces. Province-level random effects absorb unobserved territorial heterogeneity. This two-level structure is validated by the exploratory data analysis, which reveals strong geographical gradients in learning poverty across Italian provinces. As a robustness check, an equivalent multilevel random forest is estimated; it produces virtually identical predictive accuracy (RMSE differences of 0.001 or less), confirming that the relationship between socioeconomic status and at-risk outcomes is essentially linear.

A separate comparative analysis focuses on resilient schools – defined as schools in the bottom quartile of the socioeconomic distribution that nonetheless achieve a share of at-risk students below the first quartile for their subject. Differences between resilient and non-resilient low-SES schools are assessed through t-tests on the relevant organisational variables.

3. Main Results

The multilevel models explain between 26% and 39% of the variance in at-risk shares

through school-level covariates alone (marginal R^2), rising to 59–66% once province random effects are included. Province-level effects account for 34–52% of residual variance, with higher unexplained provincial variation for mathematics than for reading – and a marked North–South gradient throughout.

The key findings are organised by predictor category:

Socioeconomic status and prior achievement

School-average SES is consistently the largest predictor across all models: higher SES strongly reduces at-risk shares. Grade 5 reading scores emerge as the second most powerful predictor, underscoring that learning deficits accumulate well before lower secondary school and that early attainment is the strongest individual-level signal available to schools and policy-makers.

School demographics

Kindergarten attendance is a protective factor, reducing the share of at-risk students. Conversely, late enrolment (starting school older than peers) and high proportions of dialect or non-Italian language use at home are positively associated with risk. Female enrolment has opposing effects by subject – protective for reading risk, associated with higher mathematics risk – consistent with the well-established gender gap literature.

School transfers and funding

A higher rate of students transferring out of a school is positively associated with at-risk shares across all models. The share of expenditure on general (non-curriculum, non-salary) purposes is also positively linked

to risk. Funding from municipalities – a proxy for local co-investment – is a significant protective factor in reading and in the combined model.

Teacher characteristics

Teacher absenteeism (days of sick leave) is positively associated with at-risk shares across models. A higher number of permanent (tenured) teachers is a protective factor, particularly for mathematics outcomes, pointing to the importance of staff continuity for student learning.

School leadership

Greater principal experience (years in role) reduces at-risk shares in reading and in the combined models, suggesting that stable, experienced leadership is beneficial even within Italy's highly centralised governance structure.

Parental involvement

Among the parental involvement instruments tracked, the use of electronic registers for school-family communication is associated with a lower share of students at risk in both subjects simultaneously – the most demanding outcome variable.

Resilient schools: what makes the difference?

Among the 1,059 schools in the lowest SES quartile, 75 achieve reading outcomes and 98 achieve mathematics outcomes in the top quartile of their peers. Compared with other low-SES schools, resilient schools show: lower rates of late enrolment and language-barrier exposure; higher Grade 5 test scores; fewer permanent teachers (but with markedly lower absenteeism and, for maths, lower average

age); and more systematic parental engagement through electronic communication and targeted projects for families. No significant differences in principal characteristics or expenditure patterns are found, suggesting that leadership impact operates through channels not fully captured by the available administrative variables.

4. Policy Implications

The findings generate a set of actionable recommendations directed at national policy-makers, regional educational authorities, and school administrators.

Use predictive analytics for early resource allocation.

The merged INVALSI-MIM dataset enables reliable school-level prediction of learning poverty risk with administrative data alone. Policy-makers should institutionalise this approach – updating the dataset annually and using model-based risk scores to direct additional support (financial, professional, and organisational) towards the schools most likely to concentrate at-risk students.

Invest in teacher stability and reduce absenteeism.

Teacher tenure and low absenteeism are among the most actionable school-level factors identified. Policies that improve recruitment and retention in high-risk schools – through competitive compensation, targeted career development, and workload support – can have measurable effects on student outcomes, particularly in mathematics.

Strengthen early childhood education participation.

Kindergarten attendance emerges as a robust protective factor. Expanding access to and take-up of pre-primary education, especially in southern regions where participation remains lower, represents a high-leverage upstream intervention.

Leverage local funding and community co-investment.

Municipal co-funding is associated with reduced learning poverty risk. National and regional governments should design matching-fund mechanisms to incentivise local authorities – especially in disadvantaged areas – to invest in their schools, and should monitor how supplementary funds are allocated between general administration and direct curriculum support.

Scale up parental engagement, especially digitally.

Digital communication platforms (electronic registers) and targeted projects for families are positively associated with resilience in low-SES schools. Schools and regional authorities should invest in training teachers and administrators to use these tools effectively, while addressing the structural barriers – such as digital literacy and access – that can limit parental participation in disadvantaged communities.

Promote inter-school learning from resilient schools.

The identification of resilient schools – institutions that beat the socioeconomic odds – provides natural candidates for peer-learning networks. Policy-makers should facilitate formal partnerships between resilient schools and higher-risk neighbours

to transfer effective practices, rather than relying on top-down prescriptions.

Address territorial disparities with differentiated policies.

The persistent North–South gradient in learning poverty risk – and the greater within-region inequality in southern provinces – calls for territorially differentiated funding formulas and intervention thresholds. National averages mask highly heterogeneous local realities; policy evaluation frameworks must account for provincial context.

What is BRIDGE ?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

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Further Information:

Rossi, L., Soncin, M., Lema, M.L.D. et al. Schools at risk: mapping learning poverty in Italian schools. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability* 37, 357–384 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-025-09463-y>

**Funded by
the European Union**

BRIDGE is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101177154). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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